

Right Coronary Ostium Occlusion Secondary to Aortic Valve Prosthesis Implantation in a Patient On ECMO. Image In Medicine

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ABSTRACT

Coronary artery obstruction as an acute presentation is a rare complication in the context of open surgical aortic valve replacement. We present a case of acute right ostial coronary occlusion immediately after aortic valve replacement. The patient was admitted to the intensive care unit where right-sided cardiogenic shock was documented, and he was placed on venoarterial extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (VA-ECMO). He underwent urgent percutaneous revascularization, with placement of a venous blood conduit from the saphenous vein to the right coronary artery. Reported cases of coronary artery obstruction secondary to surgical aortic valve replacement with bioprostheses or mechanical prostheses are much less frequent than those reported after transcatheter aortic valve replacement. However, recognition of this complication confers timely intervention for the surgical emergency approach, together with adequate hemodynamic support, as fundamental pillars to restore ventricular function and stabilize the patient.

KEYWORDS: aortic valve, coronary sinus, myocardial revascularization.

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INTRODUCTION

Coronary artery obstruction as an acute presentation is a rare complication in the context of open surgical aortic valve replacement[1]. However, some studies have reported an incidence of 0.1–0.7%, being more frequent intraoperatively and associated with high mortality. Ostial obstruction of the left main coronary artery is, according to the literature, more common than that of the right main coronary artery, due to the anatomical level of the aortic annulus[1,2]. We present a case of acute ostial right coronary occlusion immediately after aortic valve replacement due to bioprosthesis dysfunction secondary to thrombosis. During the intraoperative period, a 23 mm SJ Masters aortic valve was

deployed, with secondary presence of ventricular fibrillation and acute right ventricular failure. The patient was admitted to the intensive care unit where right-sided cardiogenic shock was documented, so he was placed on venoarterial extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (VA-ECMO), urgently transferred to the catheterization room where acute ostial right coronary occlusion was documented, he underwent urgent percutaneous revascularization, where a venous blood conduit from the saphenous vein to the right coronary artery was placed (Figure 1AB), which led to subsequent recovery, with hemodynamic support and right ventricular function.

Fig. 1. a) Obstruction of the right coronary ostium by a prosthetic aortic valve. B) Saphenous ductus venosus, which runs from the aorta to the distal mid-portion of the right coronary artery.

DISCUSSION

Reported cases of coronary artery obstruction secondary to surgical aortic valve replacement with bioprostheses or mechanical prostheses are much less frequent than those reported after transcatheter aortic valve replacement, with incidences as high as 0.8%, and even higher in cases of valve-in-valve procedures (transcatheter implantation within a degenerated surgical bioprosthesis), with an incidence of up to 2.3% [3,4]. However, recognition of this complication allows for timely intervention in the surgical emergency setting. One of the main factors contributing to this complication is malposition of the prosthesis, while others include thrombosis or structural degeneration. After surgical repair, the clinical response focuses on the use of focused echocardiography to assess right ventricular function, along with hemodynamic support, as mechanical function improves [5,6].

CONCLUSIONS

Postoperative complications of cardiac valves require the integration of targeted echocardiographic evaluation, along with adequate hemodynamic support, as fundamental pillars for restoring ventricular function and stabilizing the patient.

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